

THE ROLE OF FINE ART IN HUMAN DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article includes the problem of developing children's identity through additional education in the modern educational process and solutions. It is in connection with this main component of the education of future generations that it develops their emotions and forms the skills for understanding the true nature of existence and its beauty. In addition, classes in fine arts form creative skills in a child, helping images in images that improve diverging and defiant thinking.*

Keywords: *personal development, fine arts, additional education system, art education, personality-oriented approach, thinking, creative abilities, creativity, color, image. It is known that fine art is one of the languages of mutual self-expression of specific people, which appeared long before our spoken languages.*

It has gone through a long evolutionary path from the symbolic designation of an object or event to the artistic and figurative transmission of emotional and intellectual experience: it passed from artists to the viewer, from generation to generation. [1]

Art is considered a very important role in human development and the life of society; we live with it from childhood and grow up. Art is a tool that has a strong influence on human development, and today it has its place in moral and life principles.

We have entered the 21st century with the social decline of mass culture. Currently, the number of smokers, alcoholics, and drug addicts is increasing. So, who are the heroes of contemporary art today? Whether he is a criminal, a murderer, or a negative character in quotes promoting an easy life, or qualities such as honor and love for humanity, remains completely unknown. A huge industry finances popular culture with garbage that fuels desires and passions alien to our nationality. Yesterday we talked about commercial films, and today the issue of

protecting the series from the box office is on the agenda. Music, poetry, works of art, and films, considered spiritual food, are used only for commercial purposes, leaving aside social ideas such as humanity and injustice. We can say that, today, art has become a tool of trade. That is why, first, we need to tell people about our great past, because without historical memory it is difficult to promote either literature or art. Therefore, in additional educational processes, close attention should be paid to the role of fine arts in the development of a child's personality. [2]

Fine art is one of the important types of human artistic creativity. Since ancient times, artists have expressed their imagination in their works. The world of art is a world of imagination and image. However, people cannot draw events and things that they have not seen or encountered. Each artist depicts everything from his own point of view. If we gather in our hearts the qualities of love, admiration, kindness, and respect, if we feel these qualities, these feelings will be reflected in our creative works. Aggressive power arises because we do not see and appreciate goodness and beauty. In this regard, the main task of parents and teachers is to prevent the danger of the decline and extinction of humanity; it is necessary to teach the younger generation the arts, including kindness and positive thinking.

Fine art is closely related to solving the problem of moral education and is reflected in the content of children's works. They consolidate a certain attitude towards the surrounding reality, and children develop skills such as observation, activity, independence, training skills, listening and completing tasks, and completing work started. It is equally important to develop in a child a sense of purpose, self-confidence, and the ability to complete a task through the ability to see its decision and result in the process of creative work. In the process of fine arts, preschool children develop a sense of friendship and mutual support. While working on an image, children often turn to each other for advice and help.

It is important to cultivate in children an aesthetic attitude toward the environment, the ability to see and feel beauty, and develop artistic taste and creative abilities. Fine art shows a person the real world of beauty, shapes his beliefs, and influences his behavior. Drawing influences the development of a sense of color and teaches you to see the beauty of combinations of different colors and shades. Modeling influences the development of a sense of form. The child feels the part and can independently give it the desired shape and change it. The application leads to a generalization of the child's figure and its expression using a silhouette.

By teaching children in an art school, the most important educational tasks are solved:

- formation of objective and universal methods of movement, development of the ability to learn.
- the ability to self-organize to solve educational problems
- individual development in the main areas of personal development.
- emotional, cognitive, self-control.

Subjects of artistic orientation play a very important role in the process of personal development and education, since they are aimed at developing imaginative thinking and creative potential in children, developing an emotional and value-based attitude toward the world.

One of the most important tasks of education is the formation of a functionally versatile personality with universal knowledge and skills not only in a specific subject. The foundations of functional literacy are laid at an earlier age, including introducing children to artistic culture, teaching them the ability to see beauty in life and emotions, deeply perceive works of art, and form their thoughts about their use. Practical skills in everyday life and project activities (both individual

and collective). These skills and abilities will undoubtedly enrich the inner world of schoolchildren and primary school students, significantly expand their worldview, and provide a more conscious and targeted perception of the world around them. [3]

The art education program combines two approaches, which are divided into historical and thematic. Students are introduced to the artistic culture of different periods, from ancient art to the present day, where children see the diversity of aesthetic principles and forms of creative expression in concrete examples related to nature, culture, and cultural features.

A person-oriented approach is used in visual arts classes because often creative tasks require an individual solution, and it is necessary to work with each child individually. Three types of enthusiasm are taken into account when building lessons.

First, social. To increase the child's reputation among his peers, praise for a completed task should not be spared.

Second, pragmatic enthusiasm. This manifests itself in the increased attention to the subject, because some children want to enter educational institutions where the main direction is art (recently, the interest of students in sports, the sociality of design).

Thirdly, when working with strong and talented children, the main attention should be focused on enthusiasm. Educational debates are conducted during lessons. For example, in a lesson on artistic

styles, you can divide students into groups, in which they prepare materials for arguments about which artistic style is the most important in world art. As you know, the truth is born in the dispute. Also, children are introduced to problematic situations or paradoxical demonstrations are organized, for example, an exhibition of real masterpieces of painting and decorative arts, and together with them, the main creative works take place. Stimulating interest in self-development and cognitive interest is one of the most important directions. For example, choosing materials for conversation through homework, creating your own "small art gallery" (reproductions, postcards, stamps), and, of course, you should try to develop strong and weak students. Although all children are considered gifted, only a few of them can truly draw. Especially among older children, self-criticism increases and a certain fear appears before creating a composition. Therefore, the goal of motivational support of the lesson is to maintain children's emotional well-being and confidence in their strengths.

A skillful and careful presentation of the material by the teacher, an individual approach allows paying attention to each student, determining his inclination, discussing the topic of the project, composition (through an essay), color scheme, and directing the work. A state of achievement is created when good or superior results are achieved and collectively valued. The level of knowledge, skill, and competence of a young artist increases with their children's creativity.

Thus, engaging in the fine arts is an important means of developing a child's personality in the additional education system. The activity of a person and, first, the activity of the cognitive-creative components of the complex structure of a person are manifested in visual activity. The task of a modern teacher is to teach children to see, feel, and describe the world in a good, beautiful, and positive way, to avoid bad and immoral aspects.

It is known that the word "Renaissance" means "return, restoration". If we look at the Western Renaissance, we see that the main goal was to restore the traditions and esthetics of ancient culture. This term can also be expressed as "prosperity, development". There is no need to repeat that human artistic thinking, science, and creativity reached the same height during the Maghreb-u Mashriq Renaissance. Also, some experts in the field write that certain renaissances have occurred in their fields. For example, there is a conclusion that this phenomenon has been observed eleven times in architecture. The Third Renaissance referred to by the head of state is a universal concept, and it is wrong to interpret it in connection with a particular field, in my opinion. This awakening and development should take place in all spheres - politics, economy, literature, art, science, education, medicine, agriculture, judiciary, culture, and other spheres, then the desired end is reached. The President drew attention to another aspect: the Third Renaissance is not a goal, but a means; a vehicle to the country we dream of building. The Renaissance is a glorious event, we should not devalue it with empty words and lofty promises. To turn it into a real phenomenon, it is enough for each of us to roll up our sleeves and work diligently in our field.

If we take the example of applied art, the stage of restoration of old values and traditions continues in this area. Now it is necessary to start new principles and creative research and bring Uzbek art and craft to the level of a world brand. As for fine art, unfortunately, the mood of stagnation has increased in modern Uzbek painting. To meet the requirements of the Third Renaissance, it is necessary to carry out serious creative reforms in this field and create extraordinary works of art. In short, there are many tasks to be completed to witness the Renaissance once again. It is clear that whether noble intentions or lofty goals become reality or not is up to us. [4]

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